

Performance Evaluation of Robots Utilizing Approximation Computing Capabilities

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Abstract—Our work explores a resource allocation problem in which autonomous robots, equipped with onboard processing units and approximation computing capabilities, are assigned to points of interest (nodes) to execute computational tasks based on workload demands. We formulate this problem as a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model to optimize robot assignments, approximation levels, and workload distribution while adhering to energy constraints. Given the scalability limitations of ILP, we propose a genetic algorithm-based heuristic to efficiently compute near-optimal solutions for large-scale scenarios. Experimental results demonstrate that our approach effectively balances energy consumption, computational efficiency, and workload execution, making it suitable for real-world applications that involve autonomous robots and real-time data processing.

Index Terms—robots, edge computing, cloud computing, approximation computing

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for the execution of high-performance workloads, such as Machine Learning Operations (MLOps), Artificial Intelligence (AI) training and inference, and large-scale data analytics, has led to the evolution of heterogeneous computing ecosystems. These ecosystems span across the IoT-edge-cloud continuum, integrating diverse computational resources with varying performance, power, and latency characteristics.

While the edge-cloud paradigm significantly expands the computing and storage capacity of traditional cloud architectures, the reliance on general-purpose CPUs often proves inadequate for fast, near real-time processing requirements. To bridge this gap, hardware accelerators such as Graphic Processing Units (GPUs), Tensor Processing Units (TPUs), and Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) have been introduced to enhance computational efficiency without compromising energy-efficiency or security. Hardware accelerators offload and optimize performance-critical tasks, reducing execution time and power consumption while improving overall system throughput. These accelerators are particularly beneficial in scenarios that demand stringent Quality of Service (QoS) metrics, such as ultra-low latency, high throughput, and real-time responsiveness. In edge computing, hardware acceleration is an essential piece for enabling efficient and decentralized processing, allowing complex workloads, to be executed closer to data sources rather than relying solely on centralized cloud infrastructures. This shift not only reduces

network congestion and transmission delays but also enhances real-time decision-making capabilities for mission-critical applications.

Beyond hardware acceleration, approximation techniques further optimize computational performance by trading off accuracy for efficiency. Approximate computing is based on the principle that many applications exhibit inherent error resilience properties, particularly in domains such as Digital Signal Processing (DSP) and Machine Learning, where high precision is not always necessary and can also lead to excessive energy consumption. Approximate computing significantly reduces computational overhead and therefore the consumed energy, while maintaining acceptable levels of accuracy. These techniques dynamically adapt computational precision based on application-specific requirements, further improving overall energy efficiency, execution speed, and resource utilization. When combined with hardware accelerators, approximation methods enable high-performance execution of resource-intensive workloads on constrained edge devices while maintaining acceptable levels of accuracy and reliability.

In parallel, modern robots rely on advanced processing units to enhance their autonomy and efficiency. Equipped with high-performance processors and hardware accelerators, they can perform real-time computations for tasks such as navigation, object detection, sensor fusion and other. These capabilities allow robots to operate in diverse environments, from industrial automation to medical and agricultural applications. By leveraging efficient computing architectures, robots can process data locally, reducing dependency on external infrastructure and improving responsiveness. As technology advances, robots will continue to evolve, becoming more adaptive and intelligent in executing complex missions.

In this work, we consider an environment where multiple robots equipped with processing capabilities can also leverage approximation computing techniques. These robots are assigned to points of interest (nodes) where they perform computational tasks based on the workload associated with each node (Fig. 1). This setup corresponds to real-world scenarios such as onboard LIDAR data processing or other autonomous decision-making tasks that rely on collected and analyzed data.

We formulate the problem of assigning robots to nodes, selecting an appropriate approximation level, and determining the fraction of workload to be processed while adhering to

Fig. 1: Robots are assigned to points of interest (nodes) where they perform computational tasks based on the workload associated with each node.

the robots' energy constraints. This is modeled as a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problem. Given the computational complexity of ILP for large-scale instances, we also propose a genetic algorithm-based heuristic to efficiently find near-optimal solutions. The ILP formulation ensures optimality when computational resources allow, making it suitable for small- to medium-scale problems where exact solutions are feasible. On the other hand, the genetic algorithm provides a scalable alternative, capable of delivering high-quality solutions with significantly reduced computation time. The choice between these methods depends on the trade-off between solution accuracy, computational cost, and problem size, making our approach adaptable to different application needs.

The remainder of this work is organized as follows. In Section II we report in previous work. In Section III-A, we define in more detail the targetted problem. In Section III, we describe the MILP mechanism, while in Section IV we present the genetic mechanism. Performance results are presented in Section V. The paper is concluded in Section VI.

II. PREVIOUS WORK

Multi-agent cloud robotics involves a system of multiple robots that collaborate and offload computationally intensive tasks to the edge or to the cloud for processing. This approach allows robots to leverage shared computing resources, enhancing their capabilities and enabling more complex tasks than individual robots could manage alone.

Resource allocation and service provisioning in multi-agent cloud robotics play a crucial role in optimizing robotic operations across various domains [1]. Since robots have limited computational and storage capabilities, integrating cloud and edge computing allows them to offload complex tasks and process data more efficiently. The interplay between edge

computing and cloud infrastructure enhances robotic performance by reducing latency and improving task coordination. Optimization techniques, such as reinforcement learning and approximation computing, help balance trade-offs between energy efficiency, task accuracy, and computational cost.

Authors in [3] design an Edge Cloud based multi-robot system to overcome the limitations of remote Cloud based system in exchanging delay sensitive data. The resource allocation for robotic workflow is modelled as a constrained multi-objective optimization problem and it is solved through a multi-objective evolutionary approach. [2] explores cloud robotics and proposes a reinforcement learning-based resource allocation scheme for efficient computing resource management. The RL approach autonomously decides request acceptance and resource allocation, reducing human intervention. Numerical results show it outperforms greedy allocation strategies. In [4] authors proposes a hierarchical auction-based resource allocation mechanism, the Link Quality Matrix (LQM) auction, for cloud robotic systems with ad hoc networks. By considering link quality, it ensures fast, scalable, and real-time resource allocation while reducing communication overhead. Empirical results show it outperforms existing methods in a joint surveillance scenario. [5] addresses Single-Task Robots and Single-Robot Tasks (ST-SR), multi-robot task allocation (MRTA) with deadlines, dynamic task generation, and robot constraints. It proposes an efficient online method using bipartite graph matching, alongside an exact ILP formulation for benchmarking. Applied to UAV-based flood response, the online method achieves near-optimal task completion with significantly lower computation costs. Case studies show strong scalability and broader applicability compared to existing methods. Also, authors in [6] report TianjicX, a neuromorphic computing hardware that can support true concurrent execution of multiple cross-computing-paradigm neural network (NN)

models with various coordination manners for robotics.

Approximate computing (AC) trades computation quality for efficiency, addressing performance demands under resource constraints [7]. A plethora of approximation techniques in software (programs, frameworks, compilers, runtimes, languages), hardware (circuits, accelerators), and architectures (processors, memories) have been proposed in the literature [8].

Approximate computing can be used for deep learning acceleration [9]. Authors in [10] investigate how approximate computing may reduce the complexity and enable the feasibility of embedded Machine Learning (ML) systems, in application domains such as Internet of Things, portable healthcare systems, and wearable devices. [11] explores approximate computing techniques for energy-efficient Machine Learning (ML), focusing on quantization, approximate multiplication, in-memory computing, and input-dependent approximate computing. These methods reduce AI system power consumption while maintaining accuracy, with software-based techniques offering flexibility and hardware-based solutions enhancing efficiency. The study highlights reliability considerations for robust AI accelerators, particularly for SoC and edge devices. Authors in [12] present an energy-efficient edge computing solution using Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) and Fully Autonomous Aerial Systems (FAAS) to support IoT nodes' machine learning tasks. Satisfaction Games determine optimal task offloading while considering latency, energy, and accuracy constraints. FAAS is equipped with a heterogeneous approximate DNN accelerator, leveraging approximation computing to balance computational precision and throughput.

III. MIXED-INTEGER LINEAR PROGRAMMING (MILP) FORMULATION

A. Problem Formulation

We consider a scenario where a fleet of R robots, each with a limited energy capacity, is deployed to serve N nodes. Each node j has a specific workload w_j that needs to be processed. The robots can operate at different approximation levels a , which trade off energy consumption for QoS: each level corresponds to a specific energy consumption e_a and quality of service q_a . The problem is formulated as an optimization task where each robot $r \in \{1, 2, \dots, R\}$ is assigned to a specific node $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$, operates at a chosen approximation level $a \in \{1, 2, \dots, A\}$, and handles a fraction w_r of the node's workload W_n . The goal is to allocate robots to nodes in such a way that the total quality of service is maximized while ensuring that the energy consumption of each robot does not exceed its available energy level.

B. MILP

The MILP formulation aims to maximize the quality of service while respecting the energy constraints of each robot and the workload constraints of each node. The decision variables $z_{i,j,a}$ and $y_{i,j,a}$ are used to model the assignment of robots to nodes and the fraction of workload processed, respectively. The constraints ensure that each robot is assigned

to exactly one node, that the total workload at each node is not exceeded, and that the energy consumption of each robot is within its limits.

Decision Variables

- $z_{i,j,a}$: Binary variable indicating whether robot i is assigned to node j with approximation level a .
- $y_{i,j,a}$: Continuous variable representing the fraction of workload assigned to robot i at node j with approximation level a .
- $\text{workload_fraction}_{i,j}$: Continuous variable representing the fraction of workload assigned to robot i at node j .

Objective Function

The objective is to maximize the total quality of service across all nodes:

$$\text{Maximize} \quad \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^R \sum_{a=1}^A y_{i,j,a} \cdot q_a$$

Constraints

- 1) **Assignment Constraint:** Each robot is assigned to exactly one node with one approximation level.

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{a=1}^A z_{i,j,a} = 1 \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, R\}$$

- 2) **Node Capacity Constraint:** Nodes can have multiple robots assigned, but no requirement for every node to have robots.

$$\sum_{i=1}^R \sum_{a=1}^A z_{i,j,a} \leq R \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\}$$

- 3) **Workload Fraction Constraint:** Ensure the total fraction of workload assigned to robots at node j does not exceed the node's workload.

$$\sum_{i=1}^R \text{workload_fraction}_{i,j} \leq w_j \quad \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\}$$

- 4) **Energy Constraint:** Ensure energy consumed by each robot does not exceed its energy level.

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{a=1}^A y_{i,j,a} \cdot e_a \leq E_i \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, R\}$$

- 5) **Logical Constraints:** Ensure that $y_{i,j,a}$ is non-zero only if $z_{i,j,a}$ is 1.

$$y_{i,j,a} \leq M \cdot z_{i,j,a} \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, R\}, \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \forall a \in \{1, \dots, A\}$$

$$y_{i,j,a} \geq \text{workload_fraction}_{i,j} - M \cdot (1 - z_{i,j,a}) \quad \forall i \in \{1, \dots, R\}, \forall j \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \forall a \in \{1, \dots, A\}$$

Where M is a sufficiently large constant (e.g., 30 in the code).

On the other hand, the ILP method uses a parameter called *lambda_weight* for potentially adjusting the balance between energy consumption and service quality in multi-objective optimization scenarios, although its direct impact isn't explicitly shown in the objective function in the code provided. This illustrates how each method tailors its approach to solve the same core problem with different optimization strategies and considerations.

IV. GENETIC ALGORITHM FOR OPTIMIZING ROBOT WORKLOAD DISTRIBUTION

In this work, we employ a GA to solve the problem of allocating multiple robots to nodes and distributing workload fractions in a dynamic environment, under energy and quality-of-service (QoS) constraints.

The genetic algorithm (GA) is an evolutionary optimization technique inspired by natural selection. It operates on a population of chromosomes, where each chromosome encodes a potential solution to the problem. The fitness function evaluates the quality of each chromosome, guiding the selection process to favor individuals with higher fitness. Over successive generations, the population evolves through crossover and mutation, introducing diversity and enabling the exploration of the solution space. Penalties are incorporated into the fitness function to discourage infeasible solutions. This iterative process continues until a satisfactory solution is found or a predefined termination condition is met.

In the developed GA mechanism, the chromosome representation encodes a solution as a list of R tuples, where each tuple (n_r, a_r, w_r) specifies:

- **Node:** The node assigned to the robot.
- **Approximation Level:** The processing level used by the robot.
- **Workload Fraction:** The portion of the node's workload handled by the robot.

The fitness function evaluates the quality of a solution by summing the QoS contributions of all robots, penalizing solutions that violate energy constraints or exceed node workload capacities. The fitness F of an individual is computed as:

$$F = \sum_{r=1}^R Q_{a_r} \cdot w_r - \lambda \cdot \left(\sum_{r=1}^R \max(0, E_r - E_{\max,r}) + \sum_{n=1}^N \max(0, W_n^{\text{assigned}} - W_n) \right)$$

where Q_{a_r} is the QoS level corresponding to approximation level a_r , E_r is the energy consumed by robot r , $E_{\max,r}$ is the energy limit of robot r , W_n^{assigned} is the total workload assigned to node n , and λ is a large penalty factor to discourage infeasible solutions, during the evolutionary process.

The GA begins by initializing a population of random individuals, each representing a potential solution. The population

evolves over a fixed number of generations G , with each generation involving selection, crossover, and mutation operations. Tournament selection is used to choose parents, ensuring that individuals with higher fitness have a greater chance of contributing to the next generation. Crossover is performed with a probability of $P_{\text{crossover}}$, exchanging genetic material between parents to produce offspring. Mutation is applied with a probability of P_{mutation} , introducing random variations to maintain diversity in the population. After crossover and mutation, workload fractions are normalized to ensure that the total workload assigned to any node does not exceed its capacity:

$$w_r^{\text{normalized}} = \frac{w_r}{\sum_{r \in \text{node } n} w_r} \quad \text{if} \quad \sum_{r \in \text{node } n} w_r > 1.$$

After completing the specified number of generations, the algorithm outputs the best solution found, detailing each robot's assigned node, approximation level, and workload fraction. The implemented GA approach effectively balances workload distribution, energy consumption, and service quality, providing an optimized configuration for robot assignments across nodes.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

We performed an extensive set of simulation experiments in order to evaluate the developed mechanisms. Both the Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Integer Linear Programming (ILP) approaches utilize a common set of parameters to address the robot allocation problem. These include the number of robots (R), the number of nodes (N), and the number of approximation levels (A) available for processing workload. The workload at each node is represented by a list where each value corresponds to the amount of work at a specific node. Additionally, both methods factor in energy levels required for each approximation level and the quality levels associated with these approximations. The energy capacity of each robot, known as 'robot energy levels', is also a shared input, although in the provided examples, these levels are randomly generated within certain bounds.

However, the GA introduces parameters specific to its evolutionary process. These include the population size, which dictates how many potential solutions are evaluated in each generation; the number of generations, which sets how long the algorithm runs; the mutation rate, which controls the probability of random changes to solutions; and the crossover rate, which affects the likelihood of combining aspects of parent solutions to create new offspring.

In the robot allocation problem, we measure several key performance indicators to assess the effectiveness of both Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Integer Linear Programming (ILP) solutions. Workload coverage is evaluated as the percentage of each node's total workload that robots handle, calculated by dividing the sum of workload fractions assigned by the node's workload and multiplying by 100%. Energy consumption is another critical metric, defined by the total

energy used by each robot, which is the product of the energy cost of the approximation level used and the workload fraction assigned. Quality of service is gauged through the average approximation level employed or by aggregating the quality scores for all assignments. Additionally, we look at the number of robots per node to understand resource distribution, and finally, the total workload served percentage gives an overview of how much of the system’s workload is managed, computed by comparing the sum of all work served against the sum of all node workloads.

A. Basic Allocation Mechanisms

Initially, we evaluated the performance of the ILP mechanism across different scenarios. To this end, we examined an increasing number of robots, ranging from 1 to 20, serving a fixed set of 10 nodes (Fig. 2). We assumed that both energy consumption (energy levels) and computation quality (quality level) scale linearly with the approximation level (Fig. 6.a). This reflects a balanced trade-off, where higher approximation levels enhance computational quality at the cost of increased energy consumption. The workload of each node was selected from a uniform distribution [1, 20], while the robots’ energy levels were randomly chosen to be between $nodes_{minimum_workload} * min_energy_level$ and this value plus 50, ensuring each robot can handle at least the minimum workload with the minimum energy level. In Fig. 2, we observe, as expected, that the workload served along with the energy spent by the robots increases with the number of robots.

Fig. 2: Average robots’ energy and percentage of workload served as the number of robots increases.

In Fig. 3, we present details from an experimental scenario where 20 robots are deployed to handle the workload of 10 nodes. The workload varies across nodes, with nodes [6, 10] having twice the workload of nodes [1, 5]. Figure illustrates that more robots are assigned to nodes with higher workloads, while some nodes, such as node 4, remain unserved.

Next, we evaluated the impact of the robots’ available energy levels on the allocation process while keeping the number of robots and nodes constant (Fig. 4). We measured the average energy expenditure of the robots when serving the nodes’ workload, as well as their average selected approximation

Fig. 3

computing level. As robots’ energy availability increased, both metrics initially rose before reaching a plateau. Greater energy availability allows robots to serve more workload, naturally leading to higher energy consumption. Additionally, robots tend to select higher approximation levels, as these become more viable with increased energy resources. However, beyond a certain point, both metrics stabilize, e.g. reaching the maximum possible Approximation Level, indicating that the existing robots cannot serve additional workload despite having more energy, indicating that more workload can only be served by adding more robots.

Fig. 4: Average robots’ energy expenditure and average approximation level as the number of robots available energy levels increase.

B. Approximation Levels & Function

We evaluated the approximation function in terms of both the number of available levels and the characteristics of the functions. Initially, we considered identical linear functions (Figure 6.a) for both quality and energy levels (e.g., EL=[6, 7, 8, 9, 10], QL=[6, 7, 8, 9, 10]) and varied the number of available levels from 1 to 17, ensuring that the average values of the available qualityenergy level remains the same (e.g., equal to 8). Figure 5 illustrates the results from the experiments performed for 20 nodes and 10 robots, measuring the

percentage of workload served and the average approximation level (that is the index of the EL and QL arrays). We observe that the average approximation level selected for the robot's increases with the number of available approximation levels (for energy and quality) but remains noticeably lower than the average (half that of the # of available approximation levels), indicating a more energy efficient approach. The percentage of workload served also increases up to a certain point, indicating that the additional flexibility (in terms of the available approximation levels) allows more workload to be served. However, it eventually reaches a plateau due to the energy limitations of robots to serve more workload.

Fig. 5: The percentage of workload served and the average approximation level for an increasing number of available approximation levels.

We also evaluated the use of alternative functions to describe the available energy and quality levels. Specifically, we examined two exponential quality functions with different values for the growth rate parameter k : $k = 0.2$ and $k = 0.8$ (Figure 6), analyzing their impact on workload distribution and approximation behavior. This parameter controls how quickly the quality increases as the approximation level rises, influencing the trade-off between energy consumption and computational accuracy.

In the Figure ?? we evaluated two metrics the $energy_{spent}$ defined as the $workload_{served} \cdot theenergy_{level_{s}elected}$ and the $workload_{quality}$ defined as the $workload_{served} \cdot thequality_{level_{s}elected}$. Figure 7 illustrates these two parameters while varying the robots' available energy, using an exponential quality function with growth rate parameter $k = 0.2$ and $k = 0.8$, which correspond to Figures 6.b and 6.c, respectively. These results highlight the fact that the relation between the energy and the quality levels can affect the resource allocation decisions.

C. Genetic Algorithm

Finally, we compared the ILP and Genetic mechanisms. In general, we observed that the Genetic mechanism operates faster and efficiently handles larger problems (with more nodes, robots, and approximation levels), but, as expected, it sacrifices optimality. This is precisely illustrated in Figure 8,

Fig. 6: Alternative functions to describe the available energy and quality levels.

where the ILP mechanism outperforms the Genetic mechanism in both the percentage of workload served and the selected approximation level. This indicates that ILP can serve more workload while achieving higher computing quality.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed genetic algorithm offers a robust and flexible approach to solving the multi-robot task allocation problem under energy and workload constraints. By leveraging evolutionary principles, the algorithm efficiently explores the solution space, identifying configurations that maximize QoS while adhering to system limitations. The results underscore the potential of GAs in addressing complex optimization challenges in multi-robot systems, paving the way for further research into adaptive and scalable task allocation strategies.

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(a)

(b)

Fig. 7: The $energy_{spent}$ and the $workload_{quality}$ while varying the the robots' available energy for (a) $k = 0.3$ and (b) $k = 0.8$.

Fig. 8: The percentage of workload served and the average approximation level for an increasing number of available robots.

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